

Discussion Breakout 1 Room Assignments

- Breakout Room A (2E39): Institutional Funding for Open Software
- **Lightning Breakout Room 1B (4W55):** (Teams link)
Analysis libraries or domain libraries (e.g. SolarSoft, XSPEC, Sunpy, Astropy)
- Breakout Room C (2L78): NASA Cloud
- Breakout Room D (MIC 3A-3H42A): How to decide when it's time to "clone and own" vs improve a current software library to support new use cases.
- **Lightning Breakout Room 1E (2R69):** (Teams link)
Models, simulations, and related software (including pre and post processing and visualization codes) - part 1

Discussion Breakout 2 Room Assignments

- Breakout Room A (2E39): Everything 7150! (Special Hybrid Session)
- Breakout Room B (4W55): How to encourage cross-institution development to increase re-use on missions and build community bridges to enhance NASA software community production?
- Breakout Room C (2L78): Contributions to existing Open Source Software
- Breakout Room D (MIC 3A-3H42A): Open Source Modelling Software
- Breakout Room E (2R69): Data Reduction Pipelines: A common, reuseable architecture for NASA missions

Topic 1A: Institutional Funding for Open Software

Our experience has been that software is only funded when needed to meet mission requirements. When attempting to proactively maintain widely-used open-source software, there is no institutional funding or mechanism for supporting a broad customer base. How can NASA better fund capability that is depended on by dozens of missions but not owned by any of them?

Topic 1B:

Lightning presentations for this session.

Topic 1C: NASA Cloud

Should NASA build its own cloud service? This would keep from giving a lot of money to for-profit companies, and presumably would be cheaper in the long term.

Topic 1D: How to decide when it's time to "clone and own" vs improve a current software library to support new use cases.

This is an ongoing question with any software, but given NASA's funding model it becomes especially tricky.

Topic 1E:

Lightning presentations for this session.

Topic 2A: Everything 7150! (Special Hybrid Session)

How do we make compliance easier for 7150? How do we provide training for 7150? How do we make it easier to document 7150? Share your ideas and thoughts around 7150.

Scott Tashakkor, part of the team that owns 7150, will be here to answer questions.

Topic 2B: How to encourage cross-institution development to increase re-use on missions and build community bridges to enhance NASA software community production?

The mission proposal and funding process is what creates silos - missions cannot propose to do generification - its extra risk and too expensive and building up the next project with current mission money is not even legal. How can we move to a risk and funding model to encourage multi-mission and multi-institution software?

NASA software communities span wide ranges of software projects, missions, and centers. Closed-source/closed science community models leave many of these communities siloed from others, but open models encourage better communication and collaboration between communities. These new models reduce competition and reinventing the wheel. They enable community collaboration, intellectual generosity, inclusive participation, and improve times to better solutions. Open communities are also energizing to participate in. What does the software community ten years from now look like? How does it communicate, exchange ideas, and collaborate?

What tools and practices can our software communities use to build bridges between our communities both within and across centers? An example of a tool may be <https://discourse.jupyter.org/>. This can include hackathons or regular community meetings.

What barriers exist in building community within NASA centers and across NASA centers? Are they policies, tooling, or community atmosphere related?

What are the benefits and drawbacks to adopting these tools/practices?

Topic 2C: Contributions to existing Open Source Software

NASA groups rely on existing Open Source Software — e.g., DAACs rely heavily on the `xarray` Python library. We do not only, and (in my opinion) should not only, develop OSS ourselves. When and how can NASA developers contribute, help maintain, and improve such critical OSS? Can tailoring of NASA's Open Science policies, work culture, and funding empower us to help improve OSS and ensure such software continues to support NASA mission goals.

Topic 2D: Open Source Modelling Software

While a lot of the emphasis has been placed on datasets related to measurements, there hasn't been much discussion related to theoretical simulation codes and modeling efforts. These allow for interpreting collecting data and making predictions for the future. How do we connect with numerical modelers to bring open software practices to that community and allow for increased scientific reproducibility in modeling efforts.

Topic 2E: Data Reduction Pipelines: A common, reusable architecture for NASA missions

Data reduction pipelines typically follow a common pattern regardless of mission specifics. A reusable architecture for pipeline development would allow scientists to focus on writing the science parts, and would prevent the reinvention of the pipeline architecture for each mission. How can we provide such an architecture that is compatible with the fact different missions are operated at different centers and (pseudo)external institutions like JPL, JHU APL, and STScI? What tools already exist and how would we settle on just one? If we create or decide on a single architecture, how can we encourage its use?